

Overall study design

Title of the study	LiLA: Lipid Lung-based ATLAS built Through a Comprehensive Workflow Designed for an Accurate Lipid Annotation		
Document creation date	10/06/2023	Corresponding Email	carolina.gonzalezriano@ceu.es
Principle investigator	Coral Barbas Arribas	Is the workflow targeted or untargeted?	Untargeted
Institution	CEU San Pablo University	Clinical	No

Lipid extraction

Extraction method	1-phase system	1-phase system	Methanol/Water (1:1, v/v)
pH adjustment	None	Were internal standards added prior extraction?	No

Analytical platform

Number of separation dimensions	One dimension	MS Level	MS2
Separation type 1	LC	Mass window for precursor ion isolation (in Da total isolation window)	0.05
Separation mode 1 (liquid)	RP	Mass resolution for detected ion at MS2	High resolution
Detector	Mass spectrometer	Resolution at m/z 200 at MS2	30000
MS type	QTOF	Mass accuracy in ppm at MS2	10
MS vendor	Agilent	Was/Were additional dimension/techniques used	No
Ion source	ESI		

Quality control

Blanks	Yes	Quality control	Yes
Type of Blanks	Extraction blank, Injection blank	Type of QC sample	Sample pool

Method qualification and validation

Method validation	No		
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Reporting

Are reported raw data uploaded into repository?	Yes	Summary data	Identification data
Link to repository / ID to entry	http://dx.doi.org/10.21228/M8NR7C	Raw data upload	Yes
Are metadata available?	Yes	Additional comments	-

Sample Descriptions

Healthy Mice Lung Sample / Mouse / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Additives	None
Provided information	Time to freeze (min)	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Temperature handling original sample	N2	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Time to freeze (min)	0	Sample homogenization	Yes
Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes	Sample homogenization solvent	Water/Methanol=1/1 (vol./vol.)
Storage temperature	-80 °C		

Mtb+4w / Mouse / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Additives	None
Provided information	Time to freeze (min)	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Temperature handling original sample	N2	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Time to freeze (min)	0	Sample homogenization	Yes
Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes	Sample homogenization solvent	Water/Methanol=1/1 (vol./vol.)
Storage temperature	-80 °C		

Mtb+12w / Mouse / Tissues (e.g., liver, heart, brain)

Perfusion	No	Additives	None
Provided information	Time to freeze (min)	Were samples stored under inert gas?	No
Temperature handling original sample	N2	Additional preservation methods	No
Instant sample preparation	No	Biobank samples	No
Time to freeze (min)	0	Sample homogenization	Yes
Snap freezing in liquid N2	Yes	Sample homogenization solvent	Water/Methanol=1/1 (vol./vol.)
Storage temperature	-80 °C		

Lipid Class Descriptions

1) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Check isomer overlap	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name			
HG(PC,184)			
104.6067			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

1) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	No
Normalization to reference	No	Further quantification remarks	-

2) FA[M-H]⁻ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	FA	Check isomer overlap	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-H] ⁻	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name			
FA specific fragment			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

2) FA[M-H]- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

3) DG[M+NH4]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	DG	Check isomer overlap	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4]+	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -(H2O+NH3,35)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	No	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

3) DG[M+NH4]+ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

4) MG[M+NH4]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	MG	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	No
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4]+	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -(H2O+NH3,35)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

4) MG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

5) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	TG	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotation, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name			
-(H2O+NH3)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

5) TG[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

6) BMP[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	BMP	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name			
-(NH3,17)			
-(189.03)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

6) BMP[M+NH4]+ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

7) CL[M-2H]2- / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CL	Check isomer overlap	No
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Negative	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of negative (precursor)ion	[M-2H]2-	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name			
-FA1(-H) [-1]			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

7) CL[M-2H]2- / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

8) LPC[M+H]+ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPC	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H]+	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name			
HG(PC,184)			
(C5H13NO,104)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

8) LPC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

9) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPE	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -HG(PE,141)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

9) LPE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

10) LPG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPG	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -HG(PG,172)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

10) LPG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

11) LPI[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPI	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name			
-(277.0582)			
-(269.2156)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

11) LPI[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

12) LPS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	LPS	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name			
-(87.03)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

12) LPS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

13) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name HG(PC,184) -(104.6067)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

13) PC[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

14) PC O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PC O	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name HG(PC,184) -(104.6067)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

14) PC O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

15) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -HG(PE,141)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

15) PE[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

16) PE O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PE O	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -HG(PE,141)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

16) PE O[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

17) PG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PG	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -HG(PG,172)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

17) PG[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

18) PI[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PI	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -(277.0582) -(269.2156)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

18) PI[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

19) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	PS	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -HG(PS,185)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

19) PS[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

20) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	Cer	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -(H2O,18)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

20) Cer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

21) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	HexCer	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name			
-(H ₂ O,18)			
-HG(Hex,180)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

21) HexCer[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

22) SPB[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SPB	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name			
-(H ₂ O,18)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

22) SPB[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

23) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	SM	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -(184.0719)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

23) SM[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

24) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	CE	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interferece confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+NH4] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name -Cholesterol(369.3510) -NH3			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

24) CE[M+NH4]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-

25) ACar[M+H]⁺ / Lipid identification

Lipid class	ACar	Check isomer overlap	Yes
MS Level for identification	MS2	RT verified by standard	Yes
Identification level	Species level	Separation of isobaric/isomeric interference confirmed	Yes
Polarity mode	Positive	Model for separation prediction	Yes
Type of positive (precursor)ion	[M+H] ⁺	Additional dimension/techniques	-
Fragments for identification		Lipid Identification Software	Lipid Annotator, MS-Dial, LipidHunter and LipidMS
Fragment name			
-(60.0796)			
-(85.0286)			
Isotope correction at MS2	No	Data manipulation	Centroiding
MS2 verified by standard	No	Nomenclature for intact lipid molecule	No
Background check at MS2	Yes	Nomenclature for fragment ions	N/A
Did you presume assumptions for identification?	No	Further identification remarks	-

25) ACar[M+H]⁺ / Lipid quantification

Quantitative	No	Batch correction	Normalization by reference material/QC
Normalization to reference	Yes	Further quantification remarks	-